

STUDY RESULTS

EDUCATIONAL GAME TO TACKLE THE COMPLEX CHALLENGES OF CIRCULARITY

By analyzing users' decisions throughout the HOOP Trainers game, we aim to gain a deeper understanding of the citizens' perspectives on biowaste separation, their acceptance of products derived from it, and their recommendations for constructing greener and more circular cities and regions.

PARTICIPANT PROFILE

By gender

By age

HOOP TRAINERS PLAYERS

263

PERIOD

Feb 15, 2023 - Jul 7, 2023

Presented below are the results obtained in Murcia, which can be analyzed within the Biowaste Club of the region. These findings serve as a basis for transforming data into actionable improvement proposals, fostering collaborative efforts to co-create a more circular municipality.

MISSION 1

263

PARTICIPANTS

OBJECTIVE: Properly sort 10 waste items into their respective bins

Hits and misses by waste item

% ON EACH WASTE ITEM

Waste items that raised the most doubts

RANKING BASED ON THE % OF ERRORS

BIN ● Organic (in project) ● Grey/Mixed waste
 ● Blue/Paper, cardboard ● Yellow/Packaging ● Green/ecopoint

MISSION 1

OBJECTIVE: Properly sort 10 waste items into their respective bins

Hits and misses by waste item

DATA IN % WITH RESPECT TO THE TOTAL OF THE SAME GENDER

- Female
- Male
- Non binary
- I prefer not to answer

MISSION 1

OBJECTIVE: Properly sort 10 waste items into their respective bins

Wrong answer based on gender

DATA IN % WITH RESPECT TO THE TOTAL OF THE SAME GENDER

● Female ● Male ● Non binary ● I prefer not to answer

The median age based on the provided responses

MISSION 2

202

PARTICIPANTS

OBJECTIVE: Opinions on 4 questions regarding domestic waste separation

1 Key motivations behind separate waste collection

- Reduce the environmental impact of waste
- Turn waste into useful products
- Keep our city beautiful
- Pay less taxes
- None, I'm not motivated enough to recycle

2 Primary obstacles to waste separate collection indicated by users

- Lack of information
- Lack of space at home
- Distrust, all the waste is mixed
- Lack of time
- None of the above

3 Channels for obtaining information on sorting organic waste bins

- Social networks
- Website Murcia Ciudad Sostenible
- Press
- Telephone contact
- I don't know where to find it

4 Areas which the municipality should prioritize to optimize the sorting of organic waste

- Incentivize motivation and promote environmental education
- Enhancing biowaste sorting at home
- Providing more information on proper biowaste separation

* In Murcia containers are being installed to separate organic waste. I don't know how they work and where they are... How do you find out about this type of information?

MISSION 2

OBJECTIVE: Opinions on 4 questions regarding domestic waste separation

1 Key motivations behind separate waste collection

Answer preference based on gender

DATA IN % WITH RESPECT TO THE TOTAL OF THE SAME GENDER

The median age based on the provided responses

MISSION 2

OBJECTIVE: Opinions on 4 questions regarding domestic waste separation

2 Primary obstacles to waste separate collection indicated by users

Answer preference based on gender

DATA IN % WITH RESPECT TO THE TOTAL OF THE SAME GENDER

Female Male Non binary I prefer not to answer

The median age based on the provided responses

MISSION 2

OBJECTIVE: Opinions on 4 questions regarding domestic waste separation

3 Channels for obtaining information on sorting organic waste bins

Answer preference based on gender

DATA IN % WITH RESPECT TO THE TOTAL OF THE SAME GENDER

Female Male Non binary I prefer not to answer

The median age based on the provided responses

MISSION 2

OBJECTIVE: Opinions on 4 questions regarding domestic waste separation

4 Areas which the municipality should prioritize to optimize the sorting of organic waste

Answer preference based on gender

DATA IN % WITH RESPECT TO THE TOTAL OF THE SAME GENDER

Female Male Non binary I prefer not to answer

The median age based on the provided responses

MISSION 3

190

PARTICIPANTS

OBJECTIVE: Select one bioproduct type from four proposed options

- Fertilisers
- Nutrients
- Bioplastics
- Green chemical products

MISSION 3

OBJECTIVE: Select one bioproduct type from four proposed options

Answer preference based on gender

DATA IN % WITH RESPECT TO THE TOTAL OF THE SAME GENDER

Female Male Non binary I prefer not to answer

The median age based on the provided responses

